

Case studies of implementation of policies that support research software in research organisations

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This report details four case studies of research organisations that have implemented policies that support research software. These case studies were chosen from those listed in the [database of research institution policies to support research software](#) as boundary pushing examples:

1. Monash University (Business School), Australia
2. Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Netherlands
3. Helmholtz Association, Germany
4. Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

This report is one of the outputs of the combined Research Software Alliance (ReSA) and Research Data Alliance (RDA) Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software ([PRO4RS](#)) Working Group. Interviews were conducted with staff responsible for the development and/or implementation of the policy using the questions listed in the Appendix.

Case study 1: Monash University (Business School), Australia

Policy: [Research Software Standards](#) (note: whilst this is a draft, the final policy is in place but not publicly available).

This policy proposes that high quality open source software should be treated as a research output by the faculty assessment committee. The document provides associated [guidelines](#) to assist staff in making their submission for recognition of open source software as a research output.

This development of this policy was initiated in 2019 by Professor Rob Hyndman, Head of Department of Econometrics and Business Statistics in the Faculty of Business and Economics at Monash University. Hyndman's own career experience of developing research software that was not recognised highlighted the value in offering staff the opportunity to be recognised for their work in developing and maintaining research software. The Deputy Dean of Research for this faculty was supportive of the proposed policy, perhaps partly because the faculty was the biggest developer of open source software in the university.

The biggest challenge was that the policy had to fit within the existing system for assessment of publications, whereby publications were points based on the perceived quality of the journal that they were published in. In the case of publications, an agreed journal list made these points easy to assign. Consequently, a similar system needed to be designed for research software, including a peer review process.

To create a process similar to the journal and article peer-review processes, the policy requires that the committee “obtain at least one review from an anonymous and external reviewer, or at least two reviews if the submission includes no previous peer review”. It requests that submissions include any evidence of previous peer-review, such as acceptance on CRAN or via ROpenSci. These two examples are provided as they are considered to be types of peer review that have somewhat rigorous testing or review, and thus not dissimilar to peer review of an article for publication. Significant thinking was also invested to ensure that any research software being assessed was not considered as a single object - in theory the same piece of software could receive points again in a later submission based on ongoing maintenance and/or further development.

[Guidelines](#) to accompany the policy were developed in 2024 to provide more details about how to submit. These include suggestions on how to demonstrate impact; that is, that the software is useful to other researchers, not just to the authors and their collaborators: “Such evidence may be in the form of user testimonials, download statistics, or forks/stars on GitHub, for example.” Other inclusions in guidelines include a minimum level of documentation and version control, mechanisms for handling bug reports and contributions, and some plans for long-term development and governance.

The policy took more than a year to be approved within the university (although no changes were required to it), as human resources policy has to go through a number of approval processes, including by employee unions. The policy was implemented in 2022 with the expectation that junior staff would be the most likely to utilise it, although only one person has done so to date. The policy has thus had significantly more impact outside the faculty (given its groundbreaking nature as one of very few policies internationally of this nature) than within.

Case study 2: TU Delft, Netherlands

Policy: [Research Software Policy](#).

This policy outlines the requirements and responsibilities related to the publication, reusability, and copyright of research software. It was developed as a complement to the research data management (RDM) policy and aims to support researchers in making software outputs more visible and legally compliant.

Discussions about research software started before 2019, triggered by frustrations with the then-existing process for publishing software; Researchers had to request permission from the university's Innovation and Impact Centre when publishing software, however this did not make sense for researchers developing data analysis, automation pipelines, or scripts that were not a

main output but still needed to be shared. One vocal researcher from the Faculty of Applied Sciences, whose work was software-based primarily, repeatedly challenged this process. His persistence led to collaboration with the library, ICT, and legal teams to develop a clearer and less bureaucratic pathway.

Initially, the development of the policy centred on software publication for better reproducibility. However, questions about copyright ownership and legal responsibilities quickly followed. It took around a year of negotiation to reach a compromise: researchers could publish their software under certain conditions, with the university transferring copyright back to the researcher once specific criteria were met.

The policy followed the structure of the RDM policy and identified key responsibilities across stakeholders. It aimed to clarify what research software is and how it differs from educational software. It was not prompted by a central mandate but rather by shared recognition across departments that a formal approach was needed. The technical nature of the university, combined with the increasing support from data stewards and emerging research software engineering roles, contributed to the development of the policy.

The practical implementation remains challenging. The policy includes requirements related to FAIR principles, reusability, documentation, licensing, and ownership; however, tracking whether these are followed is challenging. A decision tree was created to help researchers assess ownership, particularly in collaborative or industry-linked projects, but awareness of the process remains uneven. The university uses a list of pre-approved licenses, though others can be requested through consultation.

Researchers are expected to register their software in a repository such as 4TU. Research data and manually link the DOI in the CRIS system (Pure). These steps are not systematically monitored, and stakeholders are currently discussing how to improve compliance. There are no strict consequences for noncompliance, but researchers may lose certain protections or support if they bypass the policy process.

Library and legal support are exploring ways to make workflows more transparent. There is also work underway to connect local repository outputs with platforms like the eScience's Research Software Directory. Since the publication of the policy, training on software publication and licensing has expanded, and support has become more structured. The establishment of the Digital Competence Centre has brought in new perspectives, and efforts are ongoing to better surface research software outputs.

The long-term goal is to make research software more visible, especially in recognition and reward systems. Still, it is recognized that the RDM policy implementation is more advanced, but research software policy work is gaining traction. Challenges such as the legal implications of AI tools, clarity on copyright waivers, and consistent registration remain under discussion. Nevertheless, the policy represents a significant institutional step towards supporting research software as a research output.

Case study 3: Helmholtz Association, Germany

Policy: [Model Policy on Sustainable Software at the Helmholtz Centers](#).

This model policy was created on the basis of existing documents inside the Helmholtz Association. The template was created by the Research Software Task Group. The Forschungszentrum Jülich policy also influenced the final version of this document.

The motivation for creating this document was to combine research software policy with support: the readers should find not only what they are expected to do, but also what they should do. This helps to provide clarity, for example on how to publish software as open source.

During the creation of the model policy, approval from the directors was secured at an early stage, so it was supported from the beginning. A wide range of stakeholders were involved in the writing process: legal department, technology transfer department, IT, library scientific institutes, etc.

With the policy in place, the workflow for publication of different outputs (journal publication, data publications, and software publications) is the same. The library serves as an observer to make sure the process is followed and that metadata has required quality. In this sense, the relationship between data, software and publication has become more clear.

The existence of the model policy has brought many benefits: when scientists reach out for support they benefit from having a clear answer, and support services benefit from having a framework to provide answers. It has also increased the visibility of research software, and in turn that may have increased its quality, but this cannot be quantified.

Another benefit of the increase of visibility of research software, is that this has allowed for research software to be the focus of scientific groups; this was not possible before, and is only possible because of the change in culture to recognise the importance of software.

Case study 4: Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

Policy: [Guidelines for the development and distribution of software at Forschungszentrum Jülich](#).

These guidelines aim to support the development, management, distribution and impact of research software that meets high quality standards. The guidelines recognise software development as an intellectual achievement protected by copyright and acknowledge software developed in the context of research as an independent, first-class product of scientific work. These primarily target developers and employees who are involved in and deserve credit for this.

Forschungszentrum Jülich is one of the centres of the Helmholtz Association. Its policy was derived from the initial intention to have a universal Helmholtz policy template

(“[Model Guideline for Sustainable Research Software at the Helmholtz Centers](#)”) which could be copied and implemented at each institution. Other existing materials, such as the guidelines from the German Aerospace Center (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt), were also used. After reviewing the materials the guidelines were written from scratch but with a rough structure and all the aspects in mind. The writing process was conducted by a core writing team consisting of members representing corporate development, library and legal departments. A Software Expert Team (a diverse group of Research Software Engineers and scientists who code) were also consulted as a sounding board.

The policies were developed in a top-down way; the board of directors recognised the need for such a policy to exist, and pushed for its creation. Its implementation, however, needs support from all levels of the organisation, which is a lengthy process. It is worth mentioning that these are guidelines, and not a directive, so it is not enforced in any way. This difference is intentional and the decision was to create a guideline to allow people to adjust the guidelines as necessary. Once these guidelines have more support and have been tried and tested, they can be used as an argument to why software should be built in a particular way.

These guidelines address elements which were clearly missing in other guidelines available to FZJ researchers (for example [Regulations for Upholding Good Scientific Practice](#), Directive No. 2/2020 Publications, [Guidelines for Handling Research Data](#) and Forschung und Innovation 2025: Innovation Strategy of Forschungszentrum Jülich). They also helped clarify responsibilities and centralize information on topics which were addressed in other policies (e.g. licensing, publishing, software procurement, etc), but which made it difficult for researchers to find the right information. The goal was for these guidelines to be a “one-stop-shop” for research software topics.

The existence of the guidelines has stimulated the creation of an [RSE portal](#) (now known as the JuRSE website), and the establishment of a campus-wide support team (composed of people from research, management and legal departments), with the clear task to advertise the guidelines and provide help in implementing them (including some tooling). This is a first step toward the [implementation of the “one-stop-shop”](#) idea.

The guidelines have increased awareness for the importance of research software as a valuable research output. These changes in awareness, culture, and attention to good practices seem to indicate that these guidelines could be a directive and be easier to enforce.

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Appendix: Interview Questions

Please share the story of how and why this policy was developed. This may include points such as:

- Was the policy developed from scratch or were there existing materials within or external to the organisation that were helpful?
- Why does the policy address this list of topics related to research software? Are there other policies in these organisations that relate to other aspects of research software?
- What was the process for getting this approved, e.g. which internal stakeholders did you need to buy in to be able to go ahead with the development and implementation of this, and how did you achieve this?
- Is there now a process in place to enable implementation and/or check compliance with the policy?
- What has been the observed effect of implementing these policies in your organisation
- How would you undertake the development of this policy differently with what you know now?